

Exploring titanium based anode materials for M ion batteries (M = Li/Na)

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Abstract

Lithium ion batteries (LiBs) have been at the major research focus of energy storage since the early 90s. Lately, its ubiquitous overuse in portable electronics and rising cost has paved way for research on earth-abundant sodium ion batteries (SiBs), whereby finding new redox active materials have become imperative. A myriad of mid-range voltages can be accessed through the same Ti^{4+}/Ti^{3+} redox couple in different Ti based compounds. This is due to their diversity in structural framework and chemically dependent ionicity of the Ti-O bond. They offer ample scope for use both in LiBs, as anodes and cathodes, in SiBs, as anodes and bipolar electrodes in $NaTi_xM_yO_2$ (M=Cr/Mn/Fe/Co/Ni/Ru) with the additional M redox activating in the positive electrode (1). The mid voltage regime helps safely prevent risk of plating and a low volume change ensures extreme rate capabilities. This is best seen in $Li_4Ti_5O_{12}$ defect spinel and $MLi_2Ti_6O_{14}$ (M=2Na, Sr, Pb) that reversibly store lithium in a fast stable bi-phase flat plateau with very low polarization. Our group has taken a significant step toward by showing good reversible lithium intercalation in $SrLi_2Ti_6O_{14}$ and $Na_2Li_2Ti_6O_{14}$ (2,3), synthesized in energy efficient, combustion and sonochemical synthesis requiring very low temperature and time. Selecting anodes and cathodes with a wider voltage window maximizes the energy density. A way to do this is by reducing the voltage of anodes. However, due to the inactivity of graphite and a progressive capacity fade seen in hard carbon, increasing effort is directed towards finding new suitable low voltage anode materials. In this regard, similar to $Na_2Ti_3O_7$ introduced in 2011 (0.3V, 200 mAh/g), our group has shown good reversible sodium intercalation in combustion synthesized $Na_2Ti_6O_{13}$ (40 mAh/g, 0.83V), further extending it as proof of concept thin film batteries for the first time (4). All these along with more recent work on $PbTi_3O_7$ (175 mA/g, 0.5V) as SiB and $Na_2TiSi_4O_{11}$ (60 mAh/g, 0.5V) as LiB shall be discussed.

References

1. Patoux, Masquelier, *Chemistry of Materials*, 2002 (14) 5057
2. Guo et al, *Energy Environmental Science*, 2016 (9) 2978
3. Ghosh et al, *Journal of Power Sources*, 2015 (296) 276
4. Ghosh et al, *Journal of Electrochemical Society*, 2017 (9) A1881